

UNITS OF WORD FRAMEWORKS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article is intended to identify the usage of length measurement units in the English and Uzbek languages. It expresses huge importance of studying the units of distance measurement by giving citations from the famous linguists' opinions. Moreover, it includes several examples used in both languages to make the ideas more clear, which can be found in fictional books as well. Comparative and descriptive methods were used in this work. At the end of this article all ideas are considered and conclusion as, the aspect of length measurement in linguistics is very broad topic and should be studied as a crucial part of linguistics in both languages, is stated summarizing key points.*

Key words: *measurement, length, distance, English, Uzbek, national units.*

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Introduction. Speaking about measurements at the initial stage of the development of human society, it should be emphasized that we are talking about objects that are commensurate with the size of the person himself. Fingers and toes were the first counting instrument for humans. The same arms, legs and the dimensions of some other parts of the body (palms, spans, finger joints) and their movements - step, arm span - served as examples of the first measures of length as Depman mentioned in the book named —Measurement and metric system. All modern science relies on measurements of observable properties of specific events or objects. Typically, a single measurement yields a number associated with a unit: for example, the number-unit pair —10 meters could be the result of a distance measurement. A number-unit pair produced by making a measurement is called a datum; when there is more than one datum, they are called data. The numerical part of a datum records unique information, while the unit tells what sort of phenomenon the information refers to: in the datum —10 meters, the —10 is information, while —meters tells us how to interpret that information. (—10 feet is interpreted differently from —10 meters; the units tell us that it describes a shorter distance.) Data produced by measurements usually have some degree of uncertainty. For example, if a ruler that is only accurate to the nearest centimeter is used to measure a distance, then it is not enough to report —10 meters; a scientist must record that the distance is 10 meters give or take 1 centimeter. Without precise measurements whose uncertainties are well-understood, science could not disentangle the web of cause and effect that is the physical world. And although science is far more than the mere accumulation of measurements, without measurement science could not exist. Millions of phenomena are measured throughout all scientific fields: the weight of a mouse, the response time of a human subject, the brightness of a star, the temperature of a breeze.

Materials and methods. The concepts of length, volume, weight, mass, which are the most important in life practice, are universal in nature. They originated in people in ancient times and have come a long way of development and improvement before they became scientific terms. According to I.P. Zemskova, —some scientific, including mathematical, concepts have a cultural background [2]. The measurement of distance is one of the most fundamental tools of science. Around 2000 BC, the Sumerians began using a cubit as a standard measurement for length. A Sumerian cubit was the distance from a person's middle finger to the elbow, and a —foot [1] equaled two-thirds of a cubit. In the ancient Near Eastern city of Nippur, a copper bar was a standard measurement tool around 1900 BC. At 3.62 ft (110.35 cm) long (converting to today's measurements), the bar was divided into 4 —feet, [1] each with 16 —inches [1].

Results. There are some units of length measurement that are commonly used and recognized, at the same time there are some units referring distance that are utilized abnormally. Although they were widely used in the past, nowadays some people just know about their existence. First we will analyze frequently applied Customary units of length and distance, which belong to English linguistics, then we will move to the seldom used ones. Inch is a unit of linear measure equal to one twelfth of a foot 2.54 centimeters. The name inch is derived from the English name for the thumb joint. Even today, this unit of measurement is used in some cases. For example, the diagonal of a television, computer, laptop, cell phone, smartphone monitor is measured in inches. The abbreviation for inches is in or ". The inch was originally defined as 3 barleycorns. It was finally standardized in the International Yard and Pound Treaty in 1959. Inch is also used to refer a very small amount or distance, but it often carries a negative meaning. The toy train is four inches long; eighteen inches of thread. I had no intention of budging an inch. This unit of leisure measurement is also used to express other quantities, in particular: (As a unit of rainfall) a quantity that would cover a horizontal surface to a depth of one inch.

(Also inch of mercury as a unit of atmospheric pressure) an amount that would support a column of mercury one-inch high in a barometer (equal to 33.86 millibars, 29.5 inches being equal to one bar). In the sentence this unit can serve as a verb, more specifically followings can be outlined: (no object, with adverbial of direction): move slowly and carefully in a specified direction: The 2,000 mourners inched along narrow country lanes; The worm inched along; The value of the stock inched up toward its all-time high, (figurative) the stock market inched ahead today; (with object and adverbial of direction) cause (something) to move in this manner: he inched the car forward.

Some phrases with inch are given in The World Book Dictionary [3]: By inches 1 only just: the shot missed her by inches. 2 very slowly and gradually; bit by bit: you can't let him die by inches like this. Every inch 1 the whole surface, distance or area: between them they know every inch of the country. 2 entirely; very much so: he's every inch the gentleman. Give someone an inch and he (or she) will take a mile – proverb: once concessions have been made to someone they will demand a great deal. Inch by inch gradually; bit by bit: inch by inch he crept along the wall. Within an inch of very close to: her mouth was within an inch of his chin. (to) within an inch of one's life almost to the point of death: he was beaten within an inch of

his life. The Origin of inch belongs to the late Old English once, from Latin uncia —twelfth part, from unus —one (probably denoting a unit) [4]. In medicine and related disciplines (anatomy, radiology, etc.) the fingerbreadth (literally the width of a finger) is an informal but widely used unit of measure. In the measurement of distilled spirits, a finger of whiskey refers to the amount of whiskey that would fill a glass to the level of one finger wrapped around the glass at the bottom. Another definition (from Noah Webster): "nearly an inch. Finger is also the name of a longer unit of length used in cloth measurement, specifically, one eighth of a yard or 4 1/2 inches.

It is known that the words depicting units of measurement have existed since ancient times and were used in times when units of measurement were not introduced based on the needs of the people. For example, words such as "chaqirim, yig'och, manzil, mil, en, qari, qarich, quloch" were used with the compounds such as "ko'z yetar yer, ko'z ko'rar yer" to describe length in Uzbek language. According to the historical sources it is known that, in ancient times, people used the human body as a unit of measurement. There are even reports that human hair has been used as a unit of length. For example: "Ahmoqni ahmoq desa bir qarich o'sadi", "Ikki dunyo bir qadam". The words "qarich" and "qadam" in these proverbs have long been used as a unit of length. "Qarich" is used to represent the distance between the fingers of the person (the distance between the thumb and the fifth, the smallest finger) and "qadam" was used to represent the distance between the steps of the person. According to the historical sources it is known that, in ancient times, people used "qadam" for land surveying and canal digging. These words are still used today in the vernacular.

Better understanding of the measurement units is very crucial. Because this topic is widely connected with not only astronomy, mathematics or building, but also it has deep connections with history, linguistics and literature. It must be emphasized that we need to give students an idea of units of measurement in the past. This is especially important in literature classes.

Conclusion. In this article various units of length measurement in the English and Uzbek languages are analyzed. It was clear that we can see them not only in the mathematical books with concrete numbers but also, they can be found in literature books and folklores. Moreover, several examples of distance measurement units were investigated, in which some measuring words may obtain more than one meanings. The aspect of length measurement in linguistics is very broad topic and can be hardly examined with the help of one article. Therefore, more research in this field is needed.

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